

The European Security and Defence Union

Climate change

**A major security issue for
Europe and the world**

Security rests on many pillars

Helga Maria Schmid,
OSCE Secretary General,
Vienna

COP28: Moving away from fossil fuels

Dr Peter Liese MEP,
European Parliament,
Brussels/Strasbourg

Combating the dramatic impact of organised environmental crime

The PERIVALLON project

by Eduardo Villamor Medina, Project Manager, ETRA, Valencia

Organised environmental crime and related criminal groups are mostly silent predators, despite being the third most lucrative criminal business in the world. Its transnational dimension, involving legal and illegal businesses from multiple countries within the entire waste-processing chain, the large range of waste products as well as the limited financial and human resources allocated to law enforcement make it a high-profit-low-risk crime. Moreover, the unmet need for court-proof remote evidence collection and disparities in legal and judicial administration weaken the prosecution's work. Illegal trafficking of waste across EU borders, such as waste from electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), as well as illegal disposal of waste on our land and water are some examples of criminal activities in the area.

Devastating impacts on society

Consequences involve devastating impacts on society at different levels, from harming the health of individuals, distorting market opportunities for legitimate business, reducing the quality of life of inhabitants of towns and cities where pollutants and waste are discarded, to the destruction of natural habitats and contamination of drinking water, as well as long term impacts on climate change. The latter include the disturbance of the ecological balance and faster depletion of natural resources. Furthermore, the embedded links to wider organised crime networks and the illegitimate use of proceeds of crime leads to further societal concerns related to the trafficking of drugs, weapons, human beings, and corruption across both businesses and public organisations.

“The project aims to improve the intelligence picture of organised environmental crime.”

Eduardo Villamor Medina

is a Project Manager at ETRA, a leading Spanish industrial group. Based in Valencia, he works on EU-funded R&D projects addressing the most critical security threats in the Union and leading the development of innovative products for public authorities and critical infrastructure operators. He has participated as Project Manager in PERIVALLON, SAFETY4RAILS and ASSISTANCE, being

the author of peer-reviewed articles in the areas of machine learning, resilience, and security informatics in law enforcement.

As reported by INTERPOL, environmental crime has become the largest source of financing for non-state armed groups and is used to sustain their engagement in conflict.

Innovations for early detection and improved investigation

PERIVALLON is a Horizon Europe co-funded Innovation Action project, entitled “Protecting the European territory from organised environmental crime through intelligent threat detections tools”. The project aims to improve the intelligence picture of organised environmental crime and unlock new capacities for Environmental Agencies, Police Authorities and Border Guards. These challenges will be addressed by establishing an Environmental Crime Observatory; providing a comprehensive understanding of the scale, scope and impact of organised environmental crime on society; and developing an environmental crime detection and forensics investigation platform at the forefront of technological innovation.

The PERIVALLON platform integrates a collection of components to a single-entry point that exploits the latest advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the fields of geospatial intelligence, remote sensing, online monitoring, and multimodal analytics. These technological components will enable new capabilities such as the automatic detection of waste disposal and pollutants on land and water based on satellite imagery, optimal inspection and characterisation of sites of interest based on imagery captured by (swarms of) Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), maritime routes prediction, or online marketplaces multimedia analytics.

Fighting environmental crime together

By means of extensive training, hands-on experience and joint exercises, the capacities of police authorities, border guards, and national and regional authorities will be improved. The PERIVALLON capabilities will be validated in four transnational operational demonstrations, including one EU agency, as well as authorities from Italy, Greece, Belgium, Sweden, Romania, and Moldova. The project contributes to the achievement of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and particularly Sustainable Development Goals 3, 13, 14, 15 and 16. Furthermore, it is aligned with the agreement reached by the Council and European Parliament on a proposed new EU law on environmental crime and is expected to significantly contribute to its implementation.

<https://perivallon-he.eu/>

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